

WHITEPAPER

CMIP6PLUS

September-2024 v1

CMIP-IPO Publication No.: 03/2024

Bibliographic Information

This report should be cited as: Mizieliński, M.S., Durack, P.J., Taylor, K.E., Dunne, J., Ellis, D., Juckes, M., Stockhouse, M. and Turner, B. (2024). *CMIP6Plus*. [online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13768495>.

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This report was reviewed and approved for publication by the WGCM Infrastructure Panel (WIP) on the 05 September 2024.

Acknowledgments

Production of this whitepaper has been led by the WGCM Infrastructure Panel (WIP) co-chairs and members, supported by staff of the CMIP International Project Office (CMIP IPO) team, hosted by European Space Agency.

The work of PJD and KET was performed under the auspices of the U.S. Department of Energy by Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory (LLNL) under Contract DE-AC52-07NA27344. It is a contribution to the science portfolio of the U.S. Department of Energy, Office of Science, Earth and Environmental Systems Sciences Division, Regional and Global Model Analysis Program. LLNL Release Number: LLNL-TR-868855.

The work of Martin Juckes was supported by NERC funding for the UK National Centre of Atmospheric Science.

Contents

1 Introduction	5
1.1 Rationale for a new interim CMIP phase	5
1.2 CMIP6 infrastructure	6
2 Infrastructure changes	7
2.1 Core components of CMIP6Plus	7
2.2 Community feedback	8
2.3 Modifications to Controlled Vocabularies	8
3 Registering for CMIP6Plus	9
References	11

1 Introduction

CMIP6Plus has been initiated by the WGCM Infrastructure Panel to facilitate sustained climate model intercomparison activities in advance of CMIP7. CMIP6Plus aims to leverage existing infrastructure, enabling modelling groups to contribute to next-generation climate science with minimal additional investment before the CMIP7 infrastructure and experimental design comes online. Changes to support CMIP6Plus are targeted at allowing generic use of the data infrastructure for other projects operating on the more continuous basis, first advocated in CMIP6 and being further developed in CMIP7.

Planning for CMIP6 began in 2013, and core inputs, such as the forcing datasets used to drive the DECK and historical experiments were specified to end in 2014, frozen for use in 2018, and are now outdated (Durack et al., 2018). Modelling groups require a mechanism by which to contribute to projects initiated post-CMIP6 but before the CMIP7 infrastructure and experimental design becomes available. This Whitepaper sets out the background and rationale for this interim CMIP phase, providing an overview of changes to the infrastructure from CMIP6.

CMIP6Plus has been designed to:

- prevent infrastructure fragmentation that would ultimately degrade our ability to support scientific progress;
- have minimal impact on the groups contributing data that are already familiar with the CMIP6 infrastructure;
- be compatible with the procedures adopted by users accessing, analyzing, and making use of the existing CMIP6 data; and
- reduce the burdens on the modelling groups and infrastructure support teams.

1.1 Rationale for a new interim CMIP phase

Model Intercomparison Projects (MIPs) are ubiquitous in climate science. MIPs have become the preferred method under which coordinated international climate model experimentation is conducted.

Since CMIP6 was defined (Eyring et al., 2016), a continued expansion of MIP activities to address enduring challenging, and new, science questions has occurred, such that [more than 40 MIPs now¹ exist](#). This expands upon the CMIP6 scope with many MIPs intending to leverage the Earth System Grid Federation for data distribution and archival (ESGF; Balaji et al., 2018; Petrie et al., 2021). However, the registration of new experiments as part of the CMIP6 era was frozen in November 2020. CMIP6Plus has been created for new, or existing, MIPs that want to pursue new simulations and data publication, but do not wish to wait for the implementation of CMIP7 infrastructure.

Without coordinated interim infrastructure, there is a concern that community MIPs would independently modify the CMIP6 infrastructure in ad-hoc ways to meet their needs (or, more radically, developing their own specialized infrastructures). When there are overlapping needs across multiple projects, there are obvious advantages of scale in relying on a single versatile infrastructure rather than

¹https://wcrp-cmip.org/mips/#mip_registration

multiple specialized infrastructures, in addition to making it far easier for infrastructure providers to configure their systems and publish new data, and downstream users to access and use the data.

There are also activities supporting MIPs, such as input4MIPs (provision of forcing datasets) and obs4MIPs (provision of high-quality observation data in model output compatible format), which are critical to facilitate, contextualize, and enhance CMIP and its societal relevance in addressing the climate change challenge. Each of these projects has largely adopted the CMIP infrastructure, but with some modifications to the vocabularies to support their specific purpose.

1.2 CMIP6 infrastructure

CMIP6Plus has been devised to enable community MIPs, and their supporting activities, to continue their use of CMIP infrastructure ensuring continuity with the past and during this current period of planning and design of the next generation CMIP7 infrastructure.

Figure 1 below demonstrates the array of relationships and interactions between the data standards, tools, services and infrastructure involved in CMIP6. Components of particular importance to underpin CMIP6Plus for ensuring continuity between the CMIP phases include the search interface, ESGF, model output files, CMOR model output specifications, CF Metadata conventions and reference-controlled variables.

Figure 1. An overview of the relationships and Interactions between the data standards, tools services and infrastructure involved in CMIP6

2 Infrastructure changes

The overall goal of the CMIP6Plus modifications of the infrastructure is to facilitate its adoption by projects initiated post-CMIP6 while avoiding any changes that might conflict with those expected to be introduced for CMIP7. Unlike CMIP6 and CMIP7, for CMIP6Plus there is no coordinated or managed Data Request (Juckes et al., 2020). MIPs will need to coordinate the list variables they wish to be contributed by modelling groups independently.

In CMIP6Plus, modifications have been made to the controlled vocabularies (CVs), Variable Definitions (MIP Tables) and the tools used to manage them. In particular, the variable definitions have been separated to support their use across multiple projects, with CMIP6Plus specific information contained within the corresponding CVs. These changes will impact various infrastructure components, which will in turn need to adapt to these specifications. Coordination of these changes is being managed by the WGCM Infrastructure Panel (WIP).

2.1 Core components of CMIP6Plus

The CMIP6Plus infrastructure supports the following six components:

- 1 Maintenance of the controlled vocabularies (CVs) underlying CMIP6, with extensions needed to accommodate post-CMIP6 activities. These core CVs act as a centralized registry serving downstream infrastructure needs in a responsive and coordinated way. link: https://github.com/WCRP-CMIP/CMIP6Plus_CVs
- 2 Provision of variable tables (and MIP table collections) in an independent form serve both modelling activities and downstream users. link: <https://github.com/PCMDI/mip-cmor-tables>
- 3 Maintenance and possible extensions of data standards documentation and key tools based on those standards (notably CMOR).
- 4 Adaptation to new projects of ESGF Publication services and search index, plus the handle service.
- 5 Provision of storage for published data, with an intention to align MIP activities with their regional ESGF services in the first instance.
- 6 Avoidance of single points of expertise by ensuring that infrastructure components are robust and supported in a sustainable way.

Alongside this, the WIP is working, subject to resources, to enable:

- 7 An extension of the citation service, including assignment of DOIs, to cover CMIP6Plus, input4MIPs and obs4MIPs published data.
- 8 Adaptation of ES-Doc Errata system to record known issues.

In the longer term (for CMIP7), planning is also beginning to determine how to evolve services related to the CMIP6 Data Request and the ES-Doc model descriptions so that they might best serve future needs. For the latest information on CMIP7, please visit <https://wcrp-cmip.org/cmip7/>.

2.2 Community feedback

Within the CMIP6 community survey and in discussion during drop-in sessions and further surveys conducted as part of the CMIP7 co-design process, a number of challenges and concerns were raised with regard to the supporting infrastructure for CMIP6. The standardisation offered by the CMIP infrastructure (CF standards, standard variables, data request, data citation and ESGF) was seen by some as becoming a wider 'climate standard' making data sharing and analysis relatively straightforward, interoperable, and enabling tools such as the ESMValTool and PCMDI metrics package. Looking forward some felt that the CMIP infrastructure could be further leveraged if automated post-processing capacity was developed, more widespread development and access to community-based analysis platforms, embracing potential cloud opportunities, and simplifying infrastructure to broaden access to more diverse users.

The CMIP6Plus infrastructure addresses four of these concerns:

1. Capacity limitations –not viable to continue to run infrastructure services provided for CMIP6.
2. Continuity risk – the individual infrastructure components of CMIP6, both within and external to ESGF, depend on development teams or individuals with specialized knowledge and experience.
3. Hosting fragmentation – hosting of infrastructure components (project, model, and variable information) by independent repositories can become unsynchronized and lead to infrastructure inconsistencies.
4. CV proliferation due to lack of flexibility – foundational CMIP6 reference controlled vocabularies (CVs) structure is not flexible enough to satisfy all downstream service needs, which has led to use of nearly identical CVs by different projects, but with sometimes conflicting and problematic differences

2.3 Modifications to Controlled Vocabularies

Following this feedback from the **CMIP6 Community survey**², community feedback and issues raised on Github, changes have been made to the **Controlled Vocabularies (CVs)**³ infrastructure. These consist of three major elements:

1. **Modifications**⁴ to the controlled vocabularies, Variable Definitions (MIP Tables) and the tools used to manage them.
2. **Registration**⁵ and approval process for new variables
3. **Registration**⁶ procedure for MIPs

Maintenance of the controlled vocabularies (CVs) underlying CMIP6, with extensions needed to accommodate post-CMIP6 activities. These core CVs will act as a centralized registry serving downstream infrastructure needs in a responsive and coordinated way. link:

https://github.com/WCRP-CMIP/CMIP6Plus_CVs

² <https://wcrp-cmip.org/cmip6/cmip6-community-survey/>

³ <https://wcrp-cmip.org/cvs-and-mip-tables/>

⁴ <https://wcrp-cmip.org/cmip6plus/#CMIP6PlusModifications>

⁵ <https://wcrp-cmip.org/cmip6plus/#CMIP6PlusRegistrationNewVariables>

⁶ <https://wcrp-cmip.org/cmip6plus/#CMIP6PlusMIPRegistration>

MIP tables and Controlled Vocabularies (CVs) have been separated to support the use of generic tables across multiple projects e.g. input4MIPs, obs4MIPs.

Minor updates to the CVs have been included and more might be made during the lifetime of CMIP6Plus. User experiences during CMIP6Plus will inform CMIP7 infrastructure development and suggestions are welcomed via the CMIP6Plus CVs GitHub repository.

CMOR has been updated. To use these MIP tables and CVs, an update to the CMOR library (the 3.8.0 or later) is necessary. This is available at: [Releases · PCMDI/cmor\(github.com\)](https://releases.pcmdi.comor.github.com/).

3 Registering for CMIP6Plus

The registration procedure is set out below and is available at: <https://wcrp-cmip.org/cmip6plus/>. It has been aligned with the requirements set out in [MIP Best Practice Guidance](#)⁷. MIPs should attempt to minimise the number of new variables where possible and the storage requirements of any additions, being mindful of the associated carbon footprint. The inclusion of high data volume variables (e.g., those on many levels and/or at high frequency) should be avoided unless there is a compelling scientific justification. For CMIP6Plus, MIPs may propose new variables and these will be agreed in consultation with the WIP. Inclusion in CMIP6Plus will not automatically result in inclusion of the variable in future harmonised CMIP data requests e.g. the AR7 Fast Track data request.

Stage 1 – Declare and register MIP intention

- Determine whether MIP timeline is aligned with CMIP6Plus (shorter term) or CMIP7 (initiating with the AR7 Fast Track activity).
- Register MIP (at <https://bit.ly/MIP-registration>).
- Develop an experimental design paper outlining the details as specified in the [MIP Best Practice Guidance](#).

Stage 2 – Engage with CMIP/WIP panels

- After registration the CMIP International Project Office (CMIP IPO) will facilitate a two-way engagement with the WIP, and CMIP Panel as relevant. The following areas will be discussed during this process (building on the information provided during registration):
 - MIPs to indicate the level of infrastructure support that is required and is available (support cannot be guaranteed).
 - MIPs to confirm sufficient modelling centre interest.
 - MIPs to confirm availability of data storage at an ESGF node, either by the MIP or through the MIP participating modelling centres and to publish data according to CMIP data standards.
 - Consultation with the WIP on experiment definition and coordinate with existing CMIP6/6Plus experiments (e.g., ensure no duplicate names and a clearly defined experimental protocol).
 - MIPs to identify any cross-MIP overlaps and identify any likely experiment co-sponsors (as was done in CMIP6).

⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10572154>

- MIPs to confirm plans for developing any required forcing datasets are sufficient.
- MIPs to suggest how their science questions may align with **CMIP Science Goals**⁸ and their is wider community interest.
- MIPs may propose new variables and these will be agreed in consultation with the WIP. Inclusion in CMIP6Plus will not automatically result in inclusion of the variable in future CMIP phases.

Stage 3 – Complete Technical Registration

- This will be conducted through the Github issues interface initially.
- Liaise with WIP co-chairs and CMIP IPO to update CVs and MIP Tables including:
 - experiment IDs and descriptions
 - models that plan to deliver data
 - new approved variables
- Ensure that updated CV content is correct and as intended.
- Await confirmation that ESGF configurations have been updated. Technical registration is then complete.

⁸ <https://wcrp-cmip.org/cmip-panel-meet-to-advance-cmip7-and-ar7-fast-track/>

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